

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

EXPANDING ACCESS TO EXTERNAL FINANCIAL RESOURCES OF ENTREPRENEURIAL SUBJECTS

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Abstract

The purpose of the- study is to expand the opportunities of business entities to access external financial resources.

The methodology of the research - theoretical and systematic analysis, systematic approach, survey methods were used in the research process.

The results of the research - as a result of the research, access to external financial resources of business entities will be expanded.

Keywords: Economic relations, small and medium entrepreneurship, cooperation, efficiency, financial resources, insurance.

Introduction. The main financial source of the entrepreneur is characterized by the production and sale of products and the provision of services. It is considered the main factor that forms and strengthens financial opportunities. Here, too, the decisive stage is characterized by such features as efficiency, regularity and organization of market relations and integration relations. The characteristics of the development of the small and medium business class depend on the effectiveness and convenience of market and integration relations. They are in two forms of market relations and interact: they sell their products and provide services; they buy means of production and labor for the production and provision of services. Both types of market relations depend on organization, regularity, supply and demand, efficient prices and competition, ultimately forming, strengthening or weakening financial opportunities.

Main text. The system of economic relations is an activity mechanism that is directly related to the efficiency of its organization and management. In order to achieve the effective results of each stage of the system of economic relations, it is considered appropriate to perform certain organizational and management tasks.

Production subjects: individuals and legal entities directly participate in the organization and management of the production stage. They choose the type of activity depending on the natural and climatic conditions and their ability. They study the demand of the consumer market. Depending on economic resources and capabilities, it buys or leases the main means of production, including agricultural land (has long-term assets), concentrates labor resources, buys raw materials and materials (has short-term assets, working capital). Financial opportunities help the entrepreneur to successfully fulfill these tasks. It organizes the production process, plans the production of products, makes commitments, interacts with subjects, ensures the fulfillment of commitments and is interested in continuing its exten-

sive reproduction. Even without realizing it, the entrepreneur himself becomes the driving force of social production.

The finished product is delivered to consumers through consumer markets at the exchange stage. Buying and selling takes place here, that is, the commercial relations of the subjects are active. This stage also has its own rules and regulations. Adhering to them, organizing and managing exchange (trade) relations also requires certain organizational and management principles. Otherwise, spontaneous relationships are formed. Consumers face difficulties in purchasing raw materials and materials, they cannot buy quality products and services. This does not create a guarantee for quality product production, it cannot increase the volume of product production. Raw materials and materials purchased at high prices increase production costs, limit financial opportunities and create a tendency toward bankruptcy. At the same time, the spontaneity of exchange (trade) relations does not create conditions for the timely sale of the products produced by the economic subjects, the quality of the products decreases as well as the sales prices, and a lot of products become damaged, waste and waste. All this does not allow to increase the financial reserves of economic subjects and causes the tendency of bankruptcy. The spontaneity of exchange (trade) relations negatively affects the normal functioning of the market economy, weakens competitiveness, and does not create conditions for the efficient use of resources. The organization and management of exchange (trade) relations is beyond the scope and authority of economic subjects. A characteristic is also manifested here that it is called public interest and its bearer is the state (its relevant and competent executive bodies). It is the relevant executive bodies of the state that perform the tasks of organizing and managing exchange (trade) relations.

The last phase of economic relations, consumer relations, is considered the carrier of social, economic and public interests. It is considered a derivative of the effective organization and management of the previous

two stages. Evaluating the satisfaction of society's needs, purposeful solution of social issues and creation of a prosperous lifestyle, sustainable and dynamic development of economic development depend on this stage. Therefore, the organization and management of exchange (trade) relations clearly manifests its importance. Active participation of both economic subjects and the competent executive bodies of the state is considered important in its implementation. At this time, it is included in the duty of economic subjects: to save raw materials and materials and not allow waste; fulfill their obligations with quality; to offer quality and cheap products to the consumer market; efficient use of available resources, etc. Duties of competent state executive bodies include: creating and improving the legislative framework; to ensure the operation of an efficient market structure and create favorable conditions for the participation of economic subjects in it; be interested in developing product and service markets; to control the quality of products and services; to provide assistance and advice in the application of scientific and technical achievements; efficient organization of foreign economic relations; periodically giving recommendations to entrepreneurs on the organization of economic issues, providing relevant services: norms and regulations for the use of raw materials and materials; classification of production costs; determination of sales prices; formation of financial resources and effective use thereof; achieving effective tax, insurance, credit policy implementation, etc. to create favorable conditions for the normal operation of production and exchange (trade) relations according to economic principles. Underlying all of this are organizational and management principles. It is important to wake them up and move them.

Thus, it is possible to conclude that the efficient operation of all three stages of economic relations, the creation of financial resources, the expansion and strengthening of opportunities, which are the basis for the sustainable and dynamic development of all levels of entrepreneurship, are very important.

The analysis of the data obtained as a result of the research suggests that the economic relations of agricultural producers in the economic regions are unorganized, the resolution of organizational and management issues is characterized by spontaneity. Agricultural producers participate only in the production of products, their sale, the purchase of raw materials and their consumption, they bear all the risks themselves, and they carry out their duties related to the solution of all issues under their own responsibility. Such an approach, first, contradicts the organization and management of production processes on a scientific basis, integration relations are carried out spontaneously, and specialization is not given due importance; secondly, they cannot increase productivity indicators, resources are not used efficiently, they cannot create abundance in the consumer market, there are delays in solving social issues; thirdly, it is impossible to reduce production costs, financial opportunities are limited, it is impossible to expand and strengthen it, a tendency to bankruptcy is formed, competitiveness is weakened, etc. negative contrasts are observed.

In the organization of modern economic relations, the formation of integration relations and their efficient organization are very important. They prefer to solve it according to the principles of scientific organization of labor and specialization. In order to ensure the exemplary organization and efficient operation of such an organizational-management form, it is preferred to create a cooperative system. Therefore, in the experience of foreign countries, the creation and development of the cooperation system is considered very important. It is considered possible to easily achieve the set goals with these methods.

In our opinion, the cooperative management method is considered the most favorable form of creating optimal integration relations and purposeful development of small and medium-sized business entities. According to Professor Islam Ibrahimov, "One of the main conditions for the economic efficiency of production in the agricultural sector consists of economic factors. Economic factors include land, material and technical resources, water, technological equipment, etc., which ensure the efficiency of production. Includes resources that reflect their use and the economic factors that drive them. The level of complex use of those resources and the formation of economic relations determine the guarantee of economic efficiency." [9, p.538] The importance of cooperation here is unparalleled.

Research suggests that, although cooperation is considered an advanced stage of integration, there are significant differences between them. Integration relations are considered primary, they have the characteristics of being able to be established spontaneously, for example, even though currently the agricultural producers of the country as a whole have integration relations with the institutions, service entrepreneurs and state bodies with which they interact, although they implement it on the basis of legislation, the point of view of the scientific organization of labor considered spontaneous. That is why all the negative (undesirable) situations are often observed. The creation of the cooperation system is based on the principle of volunteerism of various production and service areas, helping each other, performing the tasks they set before them in conditions of peace and security and it is distinguished by the characteristics of achieving the goal, awakening and mobilizing entrepreneurial skills. Under the conditions of the cooperative system, to raise productivity indicators, fully provide the consumer market with quality products, efficiently use raw materials and materials, manufactured products and avoid waste, efficiently use resources, reduce production costs and provide products to consumers at low prices, develop service areas. and in this way to ensure the development of entrepreneurship, especially to stimulate the development of its small and medium entrepreneurship class, to increase profits and incomes, to appropriately continue repeated and extensive reproduction, etc. the possibilities of becoming a reality for the effective solution of economic and social issues are expanding.

In our opinion, under the conditions of the creation of a cooperative system in economic regions, it is necessary to significantly increase the volume of production of agricultural products, to expand the processing

industries: meat slaughtering and processing, primary processing of wool, sunflower and corn, specialized service areas - supply, supply, warehousing, transportation, agro-technical and zoo-veterinary services, training and consulting services, etc., opportunities to create service subjects in the status of small and medium-sized business subjects and to improve economic-statistical research, bringing it to the level of modern requirements can become a reality.

"The entrepreneur tries to use the land, capital funds, financial resources thoughtfully and usefully, and accordingly achieves and takes advantage of it. Because he is materially interested in the development of production, he constantly thinks, thinks, searches, learns the achievements of scientific and technical progress, and tries to apply them in production. It receives information on the production of advanced equipment, fertilizers, chemicals, advanced technology, providing agrotechnical services to the soil and zoo-veterinary services to livestock and implements its production and financial activities based on them" [10, p. 57].

No matter how important theoretical-methodological approaches are in the formation and strengthening of financial resources, consideration of experience is considered as important. This can be clearly felt in the opinion of the leaders of the surveyed farms.

During the survey in farms, attention was also focused on studying their attitude to the economic measures implemented to improve their financial capabilities. Although 11 (45.8%) of the surveyed households are sure that they will improve their financial capabilities by taking a loan, 20 of them (83.3%) stated that they were not satisfied with the terms of the loan. The last indicator was 80.0% among small entrepreneurs and 100% among all medium entrepreneurs.

None of the surveyed households use the services of the insurance market, and the main reason for this is that they do not understand the importance of the insurance market and are dissatisfied with the activities of insurance agencies, do not trust them and lack confidence. However, 10 (41.7%) of them said they would like to be insured, 2 (8.3%) would like to buy their product, 5 (20.8%) said they wanted to insure their livestock and 2 (8.3%) wanted to insure production facilities. 7 of all households (29.2%) stated that they do not trust the activity of the insurance organization and do not believe that they operate fairly. 35% of small

farms and 60% of medium enterprises did not trust and did not have confidence in being insured.

As a result of research, it was determined that the state of insurance relations in agriculture is unsatisfactory. None of the surveyed households use the services of the insurance market. The reasons for the emergence of such a situation include: farm managers not having a correct idea about the essence of insurance; unsatisfactory organization of insurance services; mistrust of economic entities to insurance organizations, etc.

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